

TI-59 PROGRAMS FOR ANALYSIS OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Advanced composite materials present some special problems to the engineer. Their orthotropic nature requires four engineering constants to describe their behavior in contrast to the two required by isotropic materials. In addition, composites exhibit coupling between normal and shear deformation as well as between bending and stretching load responses. The more complicated behavior of advanced composites is usually handled using techniques of matrix mathematics, but the required bookkeeping often overwhelms the isotropic-trained engineer who is used to working with fewer terms and less complicated equations. This paper describes a set of programs to be used on a TI-59 calculator which is capable of handling much of the required "bookkeeping". The set consists of ten magnetic tape programs for the TI-59 calculator. Several of the tapes are meant to be used interactively--that is, the output from one program is required as input for another. The tapes are capable of handling laminate analyses, non-mechanical responses (caused by the curing process), and strength ratio calculations for any symmetric laminate or sandwich beam. It is hoped that by relieving the user of much of the tedious bookkeeping, these tapes will make the orthotropic material calculations which presently seem so formidable, as familiar and straightforward as those for isotropic materials.

Because of their orthotropic nature, advanced composite materials present some special analytical problems to their users. Often, it is these analytical difficulties rather than physical restrictions of the materials themselves, that become the limiting factor to the most efficient use of composite materials. For example, in designing a wing, the designer may determine that his highest loads are those in the spanwise direction and so he sizes his design to carry these loads. If the material he is using is isotropic, such as a metal, he automatically obtains the same amount of strength--and hence, the same amount of material and weight--in the chordwise direction. However, by using an orthotropic material, where the strength is a function of direction, the designer can place only as much strength, and consequently only as much material and weight, as is required in each direction. Very often though, the directional properties of advanced composites are not considered at all when using these materials. Instead, designers chose to use the materials as "quasiisotropic laminates"--laminates in which the plies are stacked in such a manner that the stiffness and strength become equal in all directions. The quasiisotropic laminate is then treated as an isotropic material for design purposes. Therefore, the potential benefits of the material have been penalized by analytical inadequacies on the part of the designer.

Although the concepts and equations for describing the behavior of orthotropic materials are not exceptionally difficult, they do require techniques of matrix mathematics. The "bookkeeping" required by these techniques can become quite formidable to the users of these materials. Not only does each potential design configuration require a great deal of calculation and time, but also, the probability for errors, when performing such a large number of calculations, is enormous.

The Materials Laboratory at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base has developed a set of ten magnetic tape programs capable of handling much of the required "book-keeping" for analyzing composite materials. These programs, which have been written to be used on the Texas Instruments TI-59 calculator, can compute material properties, non-mechanical loads and strains resulting from the curing process, mechanical forces and displacements for a given loading condition, and strength ratios for predicting ply failure, for any symmetric laminate or sandwich beam.

Table 1 outlines the function of each of the ten tapes. The tape programs are meant to be used interactively--that is, the output from one program may be required as input for another.

TAPE 1 allows the user to identify the material with which he is working. This tape allows the user to enter the fifteen material properties shown in Table 2. If desired, these input values may be converted from English to SI units or from SI into English units. Once these values have been entered (and converted, if desired), TAPE 1 will use them to calculate the reduced stiffness moduli, compliances, linear combinations of moduli, strength ratio coefficients in stress space, and strength ratio coefficients in strain space for a single ply of the material in the ply-axis system. The results of TAPE 1 are required by all other tapes.

TAPE 2, TAPE 3 and TAPE 4 deal with the computation and rotation of stresses, strains, reduced stiffness moduli, and compliances of a single ply of the material. With these tapes, the user may calculate off-axis stresses (or strains) from off-axis strains (or stresses) in either of two ways. Using TAPE 2, the user may enter the off-axis strains (stresses), rotate them into the ply-axis system, multiply by the ply-axis reduced stiffness moduli (compliances) to obtain the ply-axis stresses (strains), and rotate the results into the off-axis system. Alternately, the user may calculate the off-axis reduced stiffness moduli and compliances with TAPE 3 and then use TAPE 4 to perform the off-axis multiplication. With TAPE 3 and TAPE 4, off-axis stresses (strains) may be obtained directly from the off-axis strains (stresses). Fig. 1 illustrates these two methods.

TABLE 1

TAPE 1

Enter Material Properties
 English \rightarrow SI Conversions
 SI \rightarrow English Conversions
 Calculate Q, S, U, F, G

TAPE 2

Rotate Stresses/Strains
 $\sigma = Q\epsilon$ (ply-axis)
 $\epsilon = S\sigma$ (ply-axis)

TAPE 3

Rotate Q and S

TAPE 4

Store Stresses/Strains
 $\sigma = Q\epsilon$ (off-axis)
 $\epsilon = S\sigma$ (off-axis)

TAPE 5

Enter Stacking Sequence
 Calculate A and a
 Rotate A and a

TAPE 6

Enter Core Thickness and Stacking
 Sequence
 Calculate D and d
 Rotate D and d

TAPE 7

With TAPE 5:
 Store Loads/Strains
 $N = A\epsilon$ (laminare-axis)
 $\epsilon = aN$ (laminare-axis)

With TAPE 6:
 Store Moments/Curvatures
 $M = D\kappa$ (laminare-axis)
 $\kappa = dM$ (laminare-axis)

TAPE 8

Calculate Strains/Stresses
 in Each Ply of a Laminate
 in Ply-Axis and Laminate-
 Axis Systems

TAPE 9

Enter Environmental Conditions
 Calculate Nonmechanical Strains/
 Stresses/Loads
 Calculate Nonmechanical
 Strength Ratios

TAPE 10

Calculate Mechanical Strength
 Ratios

TABLE 2

DISPLAY	SYMBOL	NAME	UNITS	
			SI	ENGLISH
15	F_{xy}^*	STRENGTH RATIO COEFFICIENT	---	---
14	X	LONGITUDINAL TENSILE ULTIMATE STRENGTH	N/m^2	psi
13	X'	LONGITUDINAL COMPRESSIVE ULTIMATE STRENGTH	N/m^2	psi
12	Y	TRANSVERSE TENSILE ULTIMATE STRENGTH	N/m^2	psi
11	Y'	TRANSVERSE COMPRESSIVE ULTIMATE STRENGTH	N/m^2	psi
10	S	SHEAR ULTIMATE STRENGTH	N/m^2	psi
9	E_x	LONGITUDINAL MODULUS	N/m^2	psi
8	E_y	TRANSVERSE MODULUS	N/m^2	psi
7	E_s	SHEAR MODULUS	N/m^2	psi
6	ν_{yx}	MAJOR POISSON'S RATIO	---	---
5	h_o	SINGLE PLY THICKNESS	m	in
4	α_x	LONGITUDINAL THERMAL COEFFICIENT	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	$^{\circ}F^{-1}$
3	α_y	TRANSVERSE THERMAL COEFFICIENT	$^{\circ}C^{-1}$	$^{\circ}F^{-1}$
2	β_x	LONGITUDINAL MOISTURE COEFFICIENT	---	---
1	β_y	TRANSVERSE MOISTURE COEFFICIENT	---	---

METHOD 1: STRESS/STRAIN ROTATION
TAPE 2

- STEP (1): STRAIN ROTATION
 STEP (2): PLY-AXIS MULTIPLICATION ($\sigma = Q\varepsilon$)
 STEP (3): STRESS ROTATION

METHOD 2: MODULUS/COMPLIANCE ROTATION
TAPE 3 + TAPE 4

- STEP (1): OFF-AXIS MULTIPLICATION ($\sigma' = Q'\varepsilon'$)

FIGURE 1 (REFERENCE [1])

TAPE 5, TAPE 6, TAPE 7 and TAPE 8 deal with the mechanical properties of a symmetric laminate or sandwich beam. When used with TAPE 5 (which calculates and rotates the in-plane moduli and compliances for a given stacking sequence), TAPE 7 performs the matrix multiplication required to obtain the in-plane loads from the laminate strains or, conversely, to obtain the laminate strains from given in-plane loads. Used with TAPE 6 (which calculates and rotates the flexural moduli and compliances for a given stacking sequence), TAPE 7 will calculate the moments when given the laminate curvatures or the laminate curvatures when given the moments as input. Once the laminate strains (in-plane case) or curvatures (bending case) have been calculated by TAPE 7, TAPE 8 may be used to obtain the strains and stresses in both the laminate-axis and ply-axis systems, for each ply of the laminate or sandwich beam.

TAPE 9 calculates the nonmechanical responses (loads and strains resulting from the curing process) of both a single ply and a laminate. After the user enters the environmental conditions (temperature change and moisture concentration), the program calculates the resulting nonmechanical strains and nonmechanical stresses for a single ply of the material, and the nonmechanical loads and nonmechanical strains for an entire laminate. The components of the nonmechanical strains are also calculated and stored for use in the calculation of mechanical strength ratios (TAPE 10). Following calculation of the nonmechanical responses for the laminate, TAPE 9 may be used to calculate the nonmechanical strength ratios for each ply of the laminate.

TAPE 10 calculates the mechanical strength ratios for each ply of a given laminate. Before using TAPE 10, the user must calculate the nonmechanical strains with TAPE 9 and the mechanical strains with TAPE 5 and TAPE 7 or the mechanical curvatures with TAPE 6 and TAPE 7. TAPE 10 then calculates the nonmechanical strains in the ply-axis system, the mechanical strains in the ply-axis system, and the mechanical strength ratios for each ply of the laminate.

Fig. 2 shows the face of the TI-59 calculator. The tapes make extensive use of the top row of keys (Key A through Key E and Key A' through Key E') to represent various parameters such as stresses, strains, moduli, and compliances and to perform various operations such as matrix multiplication or inversion. The R/S (Run/Stop) key is used for input and output of data.

Fig. 3 shows a sample problem to be solved:

The symmetric sandwich beam shown in Fig. 3 is made of T300/5208. The beam is to be loaded in bending. It is desired to find (a) the laminate curvatures and (b) the strains and stresses in the center of each ply in the top half of the beam in both the laminate- and ply-axis systems.

The solution to the sample problem is outlined in Fig. 4. Fig. 6a through Fig. 6d show the output for the problem.

The user first enters the fifteen material properties for T300/5208 and then calculates the reduced stiffness moduli (Q_{ij}), the compliances (S_{ij}), the linear combinations of moduli (U_i), the strength ratio coefficients in stress space (F_{ij} , F_i), and the strength ratio coefficients in strain space (G_{ij} , G_i) for a single ply of the material in the ply-axis system. These calculations are performed by TAPE 1. The output is shown in Fig. 6a.

Next, the user calculates the flexural moduli (D_{ij}) and the flexural compliances (d_{ij}) for the sandwich beam in Fig. 3. TAPE 6 performs these calculations. First, the user presses Key A and enters the stacking sequence from the center of the beam outward as shown in Fig. 5. The user must enter the thickness of half the core (Z_0) and then the orientation of the first ply (θ_1) followed by the number of plies of orientation θ_1 grouped together (n_1). The user continues in this manner,

DISPLAY				
A	B	C	D	E
A	B	C	D	E
		log	CP	
2nd	INV	ln x	CE	CLR
Pgm	P→R	sin	cos	tan
LRN	$x \rightarrow t$	x^2	\sqrt{x}	1/x
Ins	CMs	Exc	Prd	Ind
SST	STO	RCL	SUM	y^x
Del	Eng	Fix	Int	X
BST	EE	()	÷
Pause	x=t	Nop	Op	Deg
GTO	7	8	9	X
Lbl	$x > t$	$\Sigma+$	\bar{x}	Rad
SBR	4	5	6	-
Stflg	Ifflg	D.MS	π	GRAD
RST	1	2	3	+
Write	DSZ	Adv	Prt	List
R/S	0	.	+/-	=

FIGURE 2

GIVEN:

MATERIAL: T300/5208
 APPLIED MOMENTS:

$$M_1 = 100 \text{ N}$$

$$M_2 = 25 \text{ N}$$

$$M_6 = 50 \text{ N}$$

FIND:

- (a) Laminate Curvatures ($\kappa_1, \kappa_2, \kappa_6$)
- (b) For center of each ply in the top half of beam:
 - (1) Laminate-axis strains ($\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_6$)
 - (2) Ply-axis strains ($\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_s$)
 - (3) Ply-axis stresses ($\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_s$)
 - (4) Laminate-axis stress ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6$)

FIGURE 3

SAMPLE PROBLEM SOLUTION OUTLINE:

TAPE 1 (Fig. 6a)

Key E	Enter Material Properties
Key A	Calculate Q_{ij} , S_{ij} , U_i , F_{ij} , F_i , G_{ij} , G_i

TAPE 6 (Fig. 6b)

Key A	Enter Stacking Sequence (Fig. 5)
Key B	Calculate D_{ij} , d_{ij}

TAPE 7 (Fig. 6c)

SBR STO Key B	Enter M_1 , M_2 , M_6
Key E	Calculate $\kappa_i = d_{ij}M_j$

TAPE 8 (Fig. 6d)

Key D	Enter θ_i , Z_i
	Calculate:
	ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , ϵ_6
	ϵ_x , ϵ_y , ϵ_s
	σ_x , σ_y , σ_s
	σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_6
Key D	Repeat for Each Ply

FIGURE 4

DISPLAY	ENTER	REMARK
0 00	.01	Z_0
0 00	-45 00	θ_1
0 00	1 00	n_1
2 00	45 00	θ_2
0 00	2 00	n_2
6 00	0 00	θ_3
0 00	1 00	n_3
8 00		

FIGURE 5

TAPE 1

KEY E

F(xy*)	-500.000-03	--
X	1.500 09	N/m ²
X'	1.500 09	N/m ²
Y	40.000 06	N/m ²
Y'	246.000 06	N/m ²
S	68.000 06	N/m ²
E(x)	181.000 09	N/m ²
E(y)	10.300 09	N/m ²
E(s)	7.170 09	N/m ²
v(yx)	280.000-03	--
h(o)	125.000-06	m
α(x)	10.000-09	°C ⁻¹
α(y)	12.500-06	°C ⁻¹
β(x)	0.000 00	--
β(y)	600.000-03	--

KEY A

Q(xx)	181.811 09	N/m ²
Q(yy)	10.346 09	N/m ²
Q(xy)	2.897 09	N/m ²
Q(ss)	7.170 09	N/m ²
Q(xs)	0.000 00	N/m ²
Q(ys)	0.000 00	N/m ²
S(xx)	5.525-12	m ² /N
S(yy)	97.087-12	m ² /N
S(xy)	-1.547-12	m ² /N
S(ss)	139.470-12	m ² /N
S(xs)	0.000 00	m ² /N
S(ys)	0.000 00	m ² /N
U(1)	76.368 09	N/m ²
U(2)	85.732 09	N/m ²
U(3)	19.710 09	N/m ²
U(4)	22.607 09	N/m ²
U(5)	26.880 09	N/m ²
F(xx)	444.444-21	m ⁴ /N ²
F(yy)	101.626-18	m ⁴ /N ²
F(xy)	-3.360-18	m ⁴ /N ²
F(ss)	216.263-18	m ⁴ /N ²
F(x)	0.000 00	m ² /N
F(y)	20.935-09	m ² /N
G(xx)	12.004 03	--
G(yy)	10.681 03	--
G(xy)	-3.069 03	--
G(ss)	11.118 03	--
G(x)	60.647 00	--
G(y)	216.596 00	--

FIGURE 6a

TAPE 6

KEY A

Z(0)	10.000-03	m
$\theta(1)$	-45.000 00	DEG
n(1)	1.000 00	PLIES
$\theta(2)$	45.000 00	DEG
n(2)	2.000 00	PLIES
$\theta(3)$	0.000 00	DEG
n(3)	1.000 00	PLIES
KEY B		
Y	0.000 00	DEG
D(11)	9.362 03	Nm
D(22)	4.692 03	l/m
D(12)	3.373 03	l/m
D(66)	3.822 03	l/m
D(16)	1.167 03	l/m
D(26)	1.167 03	Nm

d(11)	144.779-06	1/Nm
d(22)	300.700-06	1/Nm
d(12)	-100.733-06	1/Nm
d(66)	284.364-06	1/Nm
d(16)	-13.446-06	1/Nm
d(26)	-61.044-06	1/Nm

FIGURE 6b

TAPE 7

SBR STO KEY B

M(1)	100.000 00	N
M(2)	25.000 00	N
M(6)	50.000 00	N

KEY E

d(11)	144.779-06	1/Nm
d(22)	300.700-06	1/Nm
d(12)	-100.733-06	1/Nm
d(66)	284.364-06	1/Nm
d(16)	-13.446-06	1/Nm
d(26)	-61.044-06	1/Nm

M(1)	100.000 00	N
M(2)	25.000 00	N
M(6)	50.000 00	N

K(1)	11.287-03	1/m
K(2)	-5.608-03	1/m
K(6)	11.348-03	1/m

FIGURE 6c

TAPE 8

KEY D			KEY D		
$\theta(1)$	-45.000 00	DEG	$\theta(3)$	45.000 00	DEG
$Z(1)$	500.000-03	PLIES	$Z(3)$	2.500 00	PLIES
$\epsilon(1)$	113.579-06	--	$\epsilon(1)$	116.400-06	--
$\epsilon(2)$	-56.431-06	--	$\epsilon(2)$	-57.833-06	--
$\epsilon(6)$	114.184-06	--	$\epsilon(6)$	117.021-06	--
$\epsilon(x)$	-28.518-06	--	$\epsilon(x)$	87.795-06	--
$\epsilon(y)$	85.666-06	--	$\epsilon(y)$	-29.227-06	--
$\epsilon(s)$	170.009-06	--	$\epsilon(s)$	-174.233-06	--
$\sigma(x)$	-4.937 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(x)$	15.877 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(y)$	803.701 03	N/m ²	$\sigma(y)$	-48.050 03	N/m ²
$\sigma(s)$	1.219 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(s)$	-1.249 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(1)$	-847.560 03	N/m ²	$\sigma(1)$	9.164 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(2)$	-3.285 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(2)$	6.665 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(6)$	2.870 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(6)$	7.963 06	N/m ²
KEY D			KEY D		
$\theta(2)$	45.000 00	DEG	$\theta(4)$	0.000 00	DEG
$Z(2)$	1.500 00	PLIES	$Z(4)$	3.500 00	PLIES
$\epsilon(1)$	114.989-06	--	$\epsilon(1)$	117.811-06	--
$\epsilon(2)$	-57.132-06	--	$\epsilon(2)$	-58.534-06	--
$\epsilon(6)$	115.803-06	--	$\epsilon(6)$	118.440-06	--
$\epsilon(x)$	86.730-06	--	$\epsilon(x)$	117.811-06	--
$\epsilon(y)$	-28.872-06	--	$\epsilon(y)$	-58.534-06	--
$\epsilon(s)$	-172.121-06	--	$\epsilon(s)$	118.440-06	--
$\sigma(x)$	15.685 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(x)$	21.250 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(y)$	-47.467 03	N/m ²	$\sigma(y)$	-264.307 03	N/m ²
$\sigma(s)$	-1.234 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(s)$	849.213 03	N/m ²
$\sigma(1)$	9.053 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(1)$	21.250 06	N/m ²
$\sigma(2)$	6.585 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(2)$	-264.307 03	N/m ²
$\sigma(6)$	7.866 06	N/m ²	$\sigma(6)$	849.213 03	N/m ²

FIGURE 6d

entering ply orientations (θ_i) followed by the number of plies of orientation θ_i grouped together (n_i), until all ply orientations for the laminate have been entered. Following entry of each number of plies, n_i , the calculator displays the total number of plies which have been entered. (The program automatically adds the mirror image to the beam as the stacking sequence is entered; so the number which is displayed is twice the number which has been entered.) After entering the stacking sequence, the user presses Key B and the flexural moduli (D_{ij}) and flexural compliances (d_{ij}) are calculated. The output for TAPE 6 is shown in Fig. 6b.

Next the user calculates the laminate curvatures with TAPE 7. He first enters the applied moments-- M_1, M_2, M_6 --with Key B and then presses Key E to multiply the flexural compliances (d_{ij}) calculated by TAPE 6 and the applied moments (M_i) to obtain the laminate curvatures (κ_i). The output from TAPE 7 is shown in Fig. 6c.

Finally, the user uses TAPE 8 to calculate the stresses and strains in the center of each ply in the top half of the beam. He presses Key D and enters the orientation of the Ply (θ_i) followed by the distance from the top of the beam core to the center of the desired ply in units of ply thickness (Z_i). (For example, the center of the second ply is one and one-half plies above the top of the core so $Z_2 = 1.5$.) The program then calculates and outputs the ply strains in the laminate-axis system ($\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_6$), the ply strains in the ply-axis system ($\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_s$), the ply stresses in the ply-axis system ($\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_s$), and the ply stresses in the laminate-axis system ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6$) for the center of the given ply. The user should repeat the procedure for each desired ply. The output for TAPE 8 is shown in Fig. 6d.

The above is typical of the type of problem which may be solved with the magnetic tape programs. The Materials Laboratory has found these programs to be a fast, easy-to-use means of providing error-free composite calculations. In addition to their usefulness as a preliminary-design or testing-analysis tool, the magnetic tape programs can be used in short courses in composite materials. By relieving students of the need to laboriously perform all of the long and somewhat tedious matrix mathematics required to solve composites problems, more time can be devoted to grasping concepts without sacrificing the valuable experience of obtaining numerical solutions.

It is hoped that with the aid of the Composite Materials Tapes, the orthotropic material calculations which presently seem so formidable to many will eventually become as familiar and straightforward as those for isotropic materials.

REFERENCES

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